

**MODE I INTERLAMINAR TOUGHENING OF
GRAPHITE/EPOXY THROUGH INTERLEAVING**
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ABSTRACT

Toughening of interleaved graphite/epoxy composites has been investigated with DCB specimens and finite element analysis. Both thermoplastic and thermoset interleaves with a wide range of film thicknesses were considered. The added interlaminar ductility was hypothesized as being brought about by the increased opportunity for crack tip plasticity due to the presence of an interlayer. The crack tip plastic zone heights predicted from finite element stress distribution and yield criteria pertinent for polymeric materials were consistent with the experimental trends of fracture toughness versus interleaf thickness. Furthermore, the interleaf thickness corresponding to the maximum observed fracture toughness closely correlated with the situation when the plastic zone height equaled the interleaf thickness. These findings support the proposed toughening mechanism.

KEYWORDS: Composites, Polymers, Fracture, Interlaminar, Interface.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of graphite/epoxy composites in structural applications is well established. However, due to their low interlaminar fracture toughness, delamination is the most predominant and life-limiting failure mechanism in these materials. A recent method to toughen laminated composites is "interleaving" that refers to sandwiching thin layers of ductile polymeric films between the composite plies [1], see Fig. 1. The interleaf film provides enhanced resistance to crack growth [1-4] and alters

Figure 1 Interleaving technique

the local stress field around the crack tip [5-7]. It has been found that the enhanced interlaminar fracture toughness is mainly derived from the increased opportunity for the plastic zone to expand perpendicular to the crack plane [8-10]. This paper summarizes recent experimental and finite element investigations of the mode I interlaminar toughening of graphite/epoxy interleaved with thermoplastic and thermoset films [4,7,10].

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Fig. 2 shows the geometry and loading of the interleaved double cantilever beam (IDCB) specimen used for mode I fracture testing. This specimen employs a unidirectional laminate with the fiber orientation along the beam axis. All specimens were made from American Cyanamid IM7/CYCOM 1827 graphite/epoxy prepreg. The thermoset and thermoplastic interleaves, placed at the midplane of the laminates, are denoted by "TSI" and "TPI", respectively. DCB specimens without interleaves are denoted "baseline". The desired TSI thicknesses of 59, 116, 177 and 214 μm were obtained by film stacking one to four layers. The TPI's were homogeneous films with thicknesses of 16, 39, 78 and 129 μm . A site for crack propagation was obtained by embedding a 25 μm thick and about 12 mm long inert teflon film between the interleaf and prepreg. Total thickness of the specimens was kept approximately constant (3.4 mm) by reducing the number of prepreg plies for the thick interleaves, see Ref. [4]. The elastic properties of IM7/CYCOM 1827 graphite/epoxy are [4]:

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 E_1 = 149 \text{ GPa}, & E_2 = 3.4 \text{ GPa}, & E_1^f = 130 \text{ GPa} \\
 G_{12} = 7.5 \text{ GPa}, & \nu_{12} = 0.29 & \nu_{23} = 0.54
 \end{array}$$

Material properties of the interleaves are provided in Table 1.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of thermoset (FM300 HST) and thermoplastic (HXT 440) interleaves [4].

Property	Units	Thermoset	Thermoplastic
E	GPa	2.45	4.57
G	GPa	0.88	1.63
ν	--	0.38	0.40
σ_{ys}	GPa	53	138

All specimens were precracked prior to fracture testing to obtain a natural crack in mode I. However, the precracking distance was kept as short as possible, within 1 to 5 mm, to minimize possible influence of fiber bridging. The IDCB specimens were loaded at a constant displacement rate of 0.76 mm/min on a Tinius-Olsen testing machine in about 5 mm crack increments until the final crack length was approximately 80 mm. The mode I interlaminar fracture toughness, G_{IC} , was determined according to the ASTM round robin compliance calibration method [11], that provides G_{IC} values for each loading increment. Further experimental details are given in Ref. [4].

Figure 2 IDCB specimen

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

For all IDCB specimens, the onset of crack growth occurred very close to, or at the maximum load. The load-displacement response was essentially linear elastic, and crack growth occurred in a stable manner during the displacement controlled fracture testing. The edge observations of the crack growth showed that crack propagation is interfacial for all homogeneous interleaves. For the thicker, film-stacked TSI and one of the TPI's (39 μm), the microscopic examination indicated less than adequate adhesion. Fiber bridging was minor in all the IDCB specimens.

To simplify quantification of the influence of interleaving on fracture toughness, steady-state or average G_{IC} values were determined from curves of G_{IC} versus crack length (resistance curves). Fig. 3 displays average G_{IC} vs. the interleaf thickness, t_i , for specimens with adequate adhesion. The TPI enhanced the fracture toughness, G_{IC} , about five-fold over the baseline value at a thickness of only 16 μm . Thicker interleaves did not provide any further elevation of G_{IC} . The 59 μm TSI enhanced G_{IC} about 30% over the baseline. The multi-ply film stacked thicker TSI failed at low G_{IC} values in a film delamination manner due to poor adhesion between the film layers.

Figure 3 Fracture toughness versus interleaf thickness

Microscopic studies indicated extensive deformation and film pull-out for the IDCB specimens that displayed large G_{IC} values. For the specimens with poor adhesion and low G_{IC} values, very little deformation of the interleaf was evident on the fracture surfaces. Necessary conditions for a large enhancement of G_{IC} are thus adequate film/film and film/composite bond strengths.

4. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Two-dimensional finite element models of the IDCB specimen, Fig. 2, were constructed to calculate stress intensity factor, strain energy release rate, and the crack tip plastic zones as a function of interleaf thickness. The IDCB specimen was modeled in plane strain using four node isoparametric elements. Two configurations of the crack plane were considered in the

analysis, one (symmetric) where the crack is located centrally within the interleaf, and the other (asymmetric) where the crack is interfacial at the film/composite interface. Notice that G_{IC} data in Fig. 3 correspond to interfacial fracture.

It should be pointed out that the interfacial configuration adds complexities to the analysis of fracture parameters compared to the symmetric configuration [7]. Stresses ahead of a bimaterial interfacial crack tip oscillate in a small region around the crack front, which implies physically inadmissible crack face interpenetration, local mixed-mode crack loading, and convergence problems with numerical solutions for the strain energy release rate components, G_I and G_{II} , see Ref. [7]. In addition to the baseline DCB specimen, 16, 40, 80, and 128 μm thick interleaves were considered in the analysis. The finite element models employed a crack length of 20 mm and a total beam length of 120 mm. The total beam thickness was kept constant at 3.4 mm, irrespective of the interlayer thickness. More details of the finite element modeling are provided in Refs. [7,10].

Fig. 4 presents the stress distributions ahead of the interlaminar crack tip for symmetric and asymmetric TPI specimens ($t_i = 16 \mu\text{m}$). The mode I opening stress σ_y displays similar magnitudes and distributions for both crack configurations. Shear stresses τ_{xy} act ahead of the crack tip in the asymmetric configuration, Fig. 4b. Although τ_{xy} is highly localized, its presence indicates local mixed mode loading for the asymmetric specimens.

Strain energy release rate and stress intensity factor for each

Figure 4 Stress distributions for symmetric (left) and asymmetric (right) IDCB specimens

of the symmetric IDCBC specimens are given in Table 2. For thin interleaves ($t_i \leq 16 \mu\text{m}$), the energy release rate, G_I , is almost unaffected by the presence of the interlayer. For thicker interleaves, however, G_I increases over the baseline value ($G_I = 7.72 \text{ J/m}^2$). The more compliant TSI material results in slightly larger energy release rates than the TPI material. Table 2 indicates that the stress intensity factors for the symmetric IDCBC specimens are much less than for the homogeneous specimen. This feature was also observed in adhesively bonded specimens investigated in Refs. [5,6].

Table 2 Energy release rate and stress intensity factor for the symmetric IDCBC specimen, $a = 20 \text{ mm}$, $P = 1 \text{ N/mm}$.

Interleaf thickness μm	G_I J/m^2		K_I $\text{kNm}^{-3/2}$	
	TPI	TSI	TPI	TSI
16	8.16	8.27	210.6	154.0
40	8.29	8.36	212.5	154.6
80	8.49	8.56	215.0	156.5
128	8.82	8.90	219.1	159.7

Table 3 presents the opening and shearing energy release rate components, G_I and G_{II} , for the asymmetric IDCBC specimen. The results verify the mixed mode nature of the asymmetric IDCBC geometry, although the magnitude of G_{II} is very small and may be neglected for thin interleaves. The mode II contribution, G_{II}/G , increases with increased asymmetry (or interleaf thickness); however, it is relatively independent of the elastic constants of the interleaf material. Notice that the decomposition of G into G_I and G_{II} may be affected by the oscillating singularity [12-14]. Comparison of the results in Tables 2 and 3 shows that, for a given t_i , the asymmetric configuration provides somewhat larger total energy release rate, G , than the symmetric configuration.

Table 3 Energy release rate components, G_I and G_{II} , for the asymmetric IDCBC specimen, $a = 20 \text{ mm}$, $P = 1 \text{ N/mm}$.

Interleaf thickness μm	G_I J/m^2		G_{II} J/m^2	
	TPI	TSI	TPI	TSI
16	8.49	8.45	0.09	0.06
40	8.67	8.65	0.13	0.12
80	8.97	8.99	0.17	0.20
128	9.30	9.35	0.33	0.35

5. PLASTIC ZONE ESTIMATES

The height of the plastic zone, h_p , is an important parameter for the fracture toughness of interleaved composites. As discussed by Shivakumar and Crews [15], the energy dissipation associated with translation of the plastic zone during crack growth is proportional to the height of plastic zone, h_p . The plastic work should also be proportional to the yield strength.

Plastic zone dimensions in the interlayer were estimated from plane strain finite element elastic stress analysis in conjunction with yield criteria appropriate for polymeric materials. For thermoset materials that deform by shear yielding, von Mises yield criterion is considered appropriate, while yielding in amorphous thermoplastics is largely influenced by the hydrostatic stress. For the TPI material a modified von Mises criterion was employed [16,17]. For comparison, von Mises criterion was also applied to the TPI. h_p was computed at a reference strain energy release rate corresponding to the toughness of the baseline DCB specimen, $G_I = 243 \text{ J/m}^2$, see Ref. [10].

Fig. 5a illustrates the calculated plastic zone height versus interleaf thickness for the TPI specimens. For both configurations, the modified von Mises criterion provides larger plastic zone heights than von Mises criterion. Notice that for $t_i \leq 40 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$, the modified von Mises criterion predicts $h_p = t_i$, (fully yielded interleaf material). At $t_i = 16 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$, fully yielded interleaf is predicted for both crack configurations and yield criteria. A plot of h_p versus t_i for the TSI specimens is illustrated in Fig. 5b. h_p reaches larger values in the TSI than

Figure 5 Plastic zone height versus interleaf thickness for symmetric (left) and asymmetric (right) IDCBC specimen

in the TPI because of its lower yield strength, see Table 1. Only for the thickest interleaves, the plastic zone is unconstrained.

Fig. 5 shows that asymmetry of the crack reduces the plastic zone height for both TPI and TSI specimens. This is attributed to the difference between the elastic stress distributions around the crack tip for the symmetric and asymmetric IDCB specimens. In the asymmetric IDCB specimen, the composite ply below the crack plane absorbs part of the intense stress field which reduces the plastic zone size. Hence, interfacial fracture is favored based on plastic zone considerations.

The experimentally observed developments of G_{IC} with t_i for TPI and TSI, Fig. 3, correlate qualitatively with the trends of h_p versus t_i in Fig. 5. The larger magnitudes of G_{IC} for the TPI is, according to the plastic energy dissipation mechanism proposed, attributed to the larger yield strength of the TPI material. The modified von Mises yield criterion is in better qualitative agreement with the trend of experimental TPI data than von Mises criterion. However, maximum experimental fracture toughness occurs at $16 \mu\text{m}$, while the maximum plastic zone height occurs at approximately $40 \mu\text{m}$ for the TPI, see Fig. 5a. Note, however, that this comparison assumes that plastic deformation is the major energy absorbing process. Furthermore, cohesive fracture of the interleaf is inherently assumed for the symmetric crack configuration, while adhesive fracture was mostly observed in the IDCB tests [4].

For the TSI specimens, a continuous increase of fracture toughness with interleaf thickness up to $t_i \approx 80 \mu\text{m}$ is predicted, Fig. 5b, which is consistent with the experimental observations, Fig. 10. However, lack of good experimental data for the thicker TSI specimens, due to inadequate adhesion [4], prohibits full quantitative comparison.

If it is assumed that an optimum interleaf thickness, t_i^{opt} , corresponds to the situation when the composite plies begin to constrain the plastic zone, ($h_p = t_i$), the data in Fig. 5 and tabulated values of h_p in Ref. [10] can be employed to estimate t_i^{opt} . The optimum film thicknesses so obtained are listed in Table 4. Comparison with the experimental G_{IC} data in Fig. 3 shows that the optimum interleaf thicknesses evaluated for the asymmetric TPI and TSI IDCB specimens are consistent with the TPI and TSI thicknesses at maximum G_{IC} . This observation

Table 4 Optimum interleaf thickness for the IDCB specimens, $G_i = 243 \text{ J/m}^2$.

Yield Criterion	$t_i^{\text{opt}}, \mu\text{m}$ (symmetric)		$t_i^{\text{opt}}, \mu\text{m}$ (asymmetric)	
	TPI	TSI	TPI	TSI
von Mises	23	94	16	68
mod. von Mises	40	--	20	--

indicates that the plastic zone constraint is a dominant toughness limiting factor for laminated composites. However, the plastic zone size alone can not explain the fracture toughness. A significant contribution to G_{IC} must come from the surface energy contribution.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The experimental and finite element results reported herein suggest that a major contribution to the apparent interlaminar fracture toughness of interleaved composites is due to the plastic work associated with translation of the crack tip plastic zone. The presence of an interleaf allows larger plastic zones to form at the crack tip. A large yield strength of the interlayer corresponds to more plastic energy dissipation and hence larger fracture toughness. The close correlation with the computed optimum interleaf TPI and TSI thicknesses and the corresponding interleaf thicknesses at maximum fracture toughness indicates that in addition to the plastic energy dissipation, the surface energy must be considered.

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